

Studies on the Properties of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{OH}$ in Solution

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The method of preparation and the properties of a few salts of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ were described in previous communications¹. In this paper the method of formation of the free base $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{OH}$ and its decomposition in solution are presented.

Attempts for the isolation of the free base were made in two ways. In the first procedure, to an ethanolic solution of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{ClO}_4$ one equivalent of KOH was added and the solution stirred. KClO_4 was precipitated and the solution gave an intense odour of pyridine, the odour increasing with time. After one hour the solution was filtered and the deep orange-red solution was kept overnight over H_2SO_4 when a brown precipitate settled and the mother liquor was almost colourless. The precipitate appeared nonhomogeneous under microscope and its analysis gave the Re : N ratio approximately 1 : 2.

In the second procedure a fairly concentrated aqueous solution of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ was slowly passed down a column of anion exchange resin (Amberlite IR 400 of OH form) at a slow rate. The issuing solution which was free from chloride was orange-red in colour, strongly alkaline and smelt strongly of pyridine. A portion of it was precipitated with ether to give a red oil. This on keeping over H_2SO_4 lost pyridine and was converted into a dark brown substance. A second portion of the eluant was kept over H_2SO_4 overnight when it deposited a brown substance which after washing appeared heterogeneous under microscope.

Having failed to isolate the base $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{OH}$ in the pure state, attempts were made to determine its dissociation constant potentiometrically. Two stock solutions of the base were prepared by collecting the effluent after passing two solutions of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ separately through an anion exchanger (OH form). With aliquot portions the concentration of rhenium in each solution was determined. Immediately after their preparation aliquots of these solutions (and also of a solution of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ for comparison) were titrated with hydrochloric acid. The titration curves are shown in Fig. 1. The curve for each of the solutions of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{OH}$ showed two breaks. The first very sharp break which occurred on the addition of 0.62 and 0.59 equivalents of acid for the two solutions respectively, represents the complete neutralisation of the strong base $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{OH}$. At this stage the solution was still alkaline ($\text{pH} \sim 8$). On the assumption that the first stage of neutralisation is solely represented by the equation

1. M. C. Chakravorti, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 81; 1963, **40**, 1045.

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the alkaline nature of the solution can only be explained due to the presence of free pyridine, since a solution of pure $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ is faintly acidic (curve III). The second weak inflexion point which occurred on the addition of 1.40 and 1.46 equivalents of acid respectively for

Fig. 1

the two solutions (curves I and II), therefore represents the neutralisation of the weakly basic free pyridine. After the second inflexion point the titration curve followed approximately the same course as that of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$. Further addition of acid, therefore, brings about the reaction

The acid association of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ being very weak², no further break in the curve was obtained.

The actual concentration of the base $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{OH}$ in the solution prepared which also contains free pyridine is difficult to calculate, since the decomposition of the base may be a complicated process involving oxidation and disproportionation of Re(V), specially in strongly alkaline solution. However, an approximate idea of the concentration of the free base can be obtained from the concentration of total rhenium in the solution and the observation that approximately 40% of the complex base has undergone decomposition at the time of titration, since the first break in the titration curve consumed about 0.60 equivalent of acid. This is however, based on the assumption that the decomposition of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{OH}$ produces no strong base. The dissociation constant of the base could not be determined due to some uncertainties in its actual concentration. However, the strongly alkaline nature ($\text{pH} > 11$) of the solutions the concentrations of the base in which were approximately 5×10^{-3} and 4×10^{-3} M respectively, indicates that the base $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{OH}$

is a fairly strong one. This fact also explains the reason behind the failure to isolate the free base, since in strongly alkaline medium $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ decomposes with loss of pyridine.

It is interesting to note that after the first break, the second break in the titration curve consumed a further amount of acid which was approximately equivalent to twice the amount of the decomposed base. The first break for the two solutions took place on the addition of 0.62 and 0.59 equivalent of acid. Calculated values of the equivalents of acid required upto the second break on this basis are therefore $(0.62 + 2 \times 0.38)$ and $(0.59 \times 2 \times 0.41)$ or 1.38 and 1.41 respectively. The experimental values were 1.40 and 1.46 equivalents respectively. The decomposition of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{OH}$ in solution can thus be represented as

It might be noted that the analogous cyanide compound $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{CN}$ has been shown to undergo similar decomposition and the compound $\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_2(\text{CN})$ has been isolated¹. Attempts for the isolation of $\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_2(\text{OH})$ in pure state have not been successful.

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